

MULTI VAGUE HOMOMORPHISM

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Abstract

This paper introduces the concept of Multi vague homomorphism between Multi vague groups, where each element is characterized by a k - dimensional vector of truth and falsity membership values. The study extends classical group homomorphisms to settings with layered uncertainty by incorporating Multi dimensional vagueness. We establish key structural properties of Multi vague homomorphism and examine their behaviour on Multi vague normal groups. Further, the notion of Multi vague order of an element under such homomorphisms is defined and investigated. Several results are proved that demonstrate how these mappings preserve algebraic and membership structure. The findings generalize existing fuzzy and vague group theories and offer a more expressive framework for modeling algebraic systems under multiple levels of uncertainty.

Keywords: Vague set, Multi vague set, Multi vague group, Multi vague normal group, Multi vague order of an element, Multi vague homomorphism

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1 Introduction

The exploration of algebraic structures in the presence of uncertainty has emerged as a significant area of research within mathematical sciences. A major breakthrough in this domain was the introduction of fuzzy set theory by Zadeh(1965)[24], which laid the groundwork for modeling imprecise and vague information. This theory was later enhanced by Atanassov(1986)[1] through the development of intuitionistic fuzzy sets, which incorporate degrees of membership and non-membership simultaneously, offering a more flexible framework to deal with uncertainty.

Further refinement of this concept was proposed by Gau and Buehrer(1993)[8] through the notion of vague sets, which use dual membership functions, truth and falsity to describe the extent to which an element belongs to a set. This dual framework has enabled researchers to more precisely represent and analyze uncertain information where a single membership value may not be sufficient.

Building upon these foundational ideas, considerable attention has been devoted to studying fuzzy and vague algebraic structures, particularly in the context of group theory. In this regard, researchers such as Bhattacharya(1987)[12] and Demirci(1999)[7] have contributed significantly by developing and analyzing homomorphisms that preserve algebraic properties within these uncertain environments. These homomorphisms that preserve algebraic properties within these uncertain environments. These homomorphisms serve as critical tools in understanding how algebraic structures behave under transformations that respect underlying operations.

Despite these advancements, a notable limitations persists: most existing models rely on single- dimensional membership values, which may be inadequate in capturing the complexity of systems influenced by Multiple and interacting sources of vagueness. Real world applications often involve layered or multidimensional uncertainty, where a single truth or falsity value dose not suffice to represent the full scope of imprecision.

To overcome this limitation, the theory of Multi vague sets was introduced by N.Ramakrishna (2020)[17], offering a natural and powerful extension to the existing models. In this framework, each element is characterized by a \mathbf{k} vector of truth and falsity membership values.This richer structure allows for a more detailed and layered representation of uncertainty, which is particularly useful in complex systems.

Extending this idea to algebraic structures, particularly groups, presents a natural and promising direction. The extensionof Multi vague sets to group homomorphism enables the modelling of transformations that preserve group operations while accounting for Multi dimensional vagueness. This provides a more robust mathematical framework for analysing group theoretic behaviour in uncertain environments.

In present work, we aim to formalize the notion of Multi vague group homomorphisms of dimension \mathbf{k} , and investigate their core algebraic properties. We explore how these homomorphisms maintain the structural integrity of multi vague groups and demonstrate that they generalize classical fuzzy and vague homomorphisms. Furthermore, this study opens new avenues for future research by providing a mathematical

foundation for analyzing algebraic structures under Multi layered uncertainty, thereby offering deeper insights into uncertainty in abstract algebra.

2 Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 A Vague set A in the universe of discourse X is a pair (t_A, f_A) where $t_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $f_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, are the mappings such that $t_A(x) + f_A(x) \leq 1$, for all $x \in X$. The functions $t_A(x)$ and $f_A(x)$ are called true and false membership functions respectively.

Definition 2.2 Let X be a non-empty set. A vague set $A = (t_A, f_A)$ where $t_A(x) = (t_{1A}(x), t_{2A}(x), \dots, t_{kA}(x))$ and $f_A(x) = (f_{1A}(x), f_{2A}(x), \dots, f_{kA}(x))$ and $t_{iA} : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $f_{iA} : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, are mappings such that $t_{iA}(x) + f_{iA}(x) \leq 1$, for all $x \in X$, for $i=1,2,3,\dots,k$ is called Multi vague set of X with dimension k . Here $t_{1A}(x) \geq t_{2A}(x) \geq \dots t_{kA}(x)$, for all $x \in X$.

Note: We arranged the true membership sequence is decreasing order, then the corresponding false membership sequence need not be in decreasing or increasing order.

Example 2.3 Consider a group $G = \{1, \omega, \omega^2\}$ with usual multiplication.

$$A = \{ \langle 1, (0.6, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2), (0.3, 0.5, 0.4, 0.4) \rangle, \\ \langle \omega, (0.6, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1), (0.2, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2) \rangle, \\ \langle \omega^2, (0.5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2), (0.3, 0.4, 0.2, 0.6) \rangle \}$$

is a Multi vague set.

Definition 2.4 A Multi vague set $A = (t_A, f_A)$ of dimension k of a group G is said to be a Multi vague group of G if, for all $x, y \in G$,

- 1 $t_A(xy) \geq t_A(x) \wedge t_A(y)$ and $t_A(x^{-1}) = t_A(x)$
- 2 $f_A(xy) \leq f_A(x) \vee f_A(y)$ and $f_A(x^{-1}) = f_A(x)$

i.e.,

- 1 $t_{iA}(xy) \geq t_{iA}(x) \wedge t_{iA}(y)$ and $t_{iA}(x^{-1}) = t_{iA}(x)$
- 2 $f_{iA}(xy) \leq f_{iA}(x) \vee f_{iA}(y)$ and $f_{iA}(x^{-1}) = f_{iA}(x)$ for all $i=1,2,3,\dots,k$.

Equivalently, we define Multi vague group as, for all $x, y \in G$, $t_{iA}(xy^{-1}) \geq t_{iA}(x) \wedge t_{iA}(y)$, and $f_{iA}(xy^{-1}) \leq f_{iA}(x) \vee f_{iA}(y)$, and $i=1,2,\dots,k$.

Theorem 2.5 Let A be a Multi vague group of a group G then $t_A(xy^{-1}) = t_A(e)$ and $f_A(xy^{-1}) = f_A(e) \Rightarrow t_A(x) = t_A(y)$ and $f_A(x) = f_A(y)$.

Definition 2.6 Let $A = (t_A, f_A)$ be a Multi vague set of a non-empty set G . where $t_A(x) = (t_{1A}(x), t_{2A}(x), \dots, t_{kA}(x))$ and $f_A(x) = (f_{1A}(x), f_{2A}(x), \dots, f_{kA}(x))$ and $\alpha = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_k), \beta = (\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_k)$ where $0 \leq \alpha_i + \beta_i \leq 1$, for $i=1, 2, \dots, k$. Then (α, β) - cut of A is defined as $A_{[\alpha, \beta]} = \{x \mid x \in G, t_{iA}(x) \geq \alpha, f_{iA}(x) \leq \beta\}$. It is a crisp Multi set.

Definition 2.7 Let X be a non-empty set. A vague group A is a pair (t_A, f_A) of dimension k of a group G is said to be a Multi vague normal group of $G, \forall x, g \in G$.

$$t_A(x) \leq \wedge t_A(gxg^{-1}) \text{ and } f_A(x) \geq \vee f_A(gxg^{-1})$$

$$\text{i.e., } t_{iA}(x) \leq \wedge t_{iA}(gxg^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k \text{ and } f_{iA}(x) \geq \vee f_{iA}(gxg^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k$$

Example 2.8 Let $G = \{1, -1, i, -i\}$ be a group. and A be a Multi vague group of G with dimension 4.

$$A = \{\langle 1, (0.7, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2), (0.3, 0.5, 0.4, 0.3) \rangle, \langle -1, (0.6, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1), (0.3, 0.6, 0.5, 0.4) \rangle\}$$

Clearly A , is a Multi vague normal group.

Definition 2.9 $GV_A = \{x \in G \mid t_{iA}(x) = t_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k \& f_{iA}(x) = f_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k\}$ is a crisp subgroup of a finite group G .

Theorem 2.10 If A is Multi vague normal subgroup of a group G , then GV_A is a crisp normal subgroup of G .

Definition 2.11 Let A be a vague group of a group G . Given $x \in G$, if there exists a least positive integer n such that $V_A(x^n) = V_A(e)$, then n is called the vague order of x , w.r.to A . We denote it as $VO_A(x)$ i.e., $VO_A(x) = n$

where $A = (t_A, f_A), t_A(x) + f_A(x) \leq 1 \forall x \in G$

$$V_A(x^n) = (t_A(x^n), f_A(x^n)) = (t_A(e), f_A(e))$$

Definition 2.12 Let G be a group and A is a Multi vague group of group G with dimension k , then $A = (t_A, f_A)$ where $t_A = (t_{1A}, t_{2A}, \dots, t_{kA}), f_A = (f_{1A}, f_{2A}, \dots, f_{kA})$ with $t_{1A} \geq t_{2A} \geq \dots \geq t_{kA}$ and $t_{iA} + f_{iA} \leq 1, \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, k$, then Multi vague order of an element $x \in G$ is defined as the smallest positive integer n such that

$$t_A(x^n) = t_A(e) \& f_A(x^n) = f_A(e)$$

$$\text{i.e., } t_{iA}(x^n) = t_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k \& f_{iA}(x^n) = f_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k.$$

It is denoted by $MVO_A(x) = n$.

If no such n exists, the Multi vague order of x is infinite.

Example 2.13 Let the group $G = (Z_4, +_4)$ and $Z_4 = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$

$$A = \{(0, (1, 0.9, 0.8, 0.7), (0, 0, 0, 0))\}$$

- $\langle 1, (0.7, 0.6, 0.5, 0.4), (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5) \rangle$
- $\langle 2, (0.8, 0.7, 0.6, 0.5), (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4) \rangle$
- $\langle 3, (0.7, 0.6, 0.5, 0.4), (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5) \rangle$

Clearly A is a Multi vague group of G with dimension 4.

In Z_4 , 0 is the identity element.

- (i) $0 = 0 \Rightarrow t_{iA}(0) = t_{iA}(0) \}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{iA}(0) = f_{iA}(0) \}_{i=1}^k \Rightarrow MVO_A(0) = 1$
- (ii) $1+41+41+41 = 0 \Rightarrow t_{iA}(1^4) = t_{iA}(0) \}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{iA}(1^4) = f_{iA}(0) \}_{i=1}^k \Rightarrow MVO_A(1) = 4$
- (iii) $2+42 = 0 \Rightarrow t_{iA}(2^2) = t_{iA}(0) \}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{iA}(2^2) = f_{iA}(0) \}_{i=1}^k \Rightarrow MVO_A(2) = 2$
- (iv) $3+43+43+43 = 0 \Rightarrow t_{iA}(3^4) = t_{iA}(0) \}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{iA}(3^4) = f_{iA}(0) \}_{i=1}^k \Rightarrow MVO_A(3) = 4$

Definition 2.14 Let A be a Multi vague group of a group G , with dimension k , then the set $N(A) = \{a \in G \mid t_A(axa^{-1}) = t_A(x) \text{ \& } f_A(axa^{-1}) = f_A(x), \forall x \in G\}$ i.e., $N(A) = \{a \in G \mid t_{iA}(axa^{-1}) = t_{iA}(x) \}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{iA}(axa^{-1}) = f_{iA}(x) \}_{i=1}^k, \forall x \in G\}$ is called Multi vague normalizer of A .

3 Multi Vague Homomorphism

Definition 3.1 Let g be a mapping from a set X into Y . Let A be a Multi vague set in X with dimension k . Here $A = (t_A, f_A)$ where $t_A = (t_{1A}, t_{2A}, \dots, t_{kA})$ and $f_A = (f_{1A}, f_{2A}, \dots, f_{kA})$.

Here $t_{1A} \geq t_{2A} \geq \dots \geq t_{kA}$ and $t_{iA} + f_{iA} \leq 1, i = 1, 2, \dots, k$ then $g(A)$ is a Multi vague set in Y , with dimension k , is given by

$$t_{g(A)}(y) = \begin{cases} \sup\{t_{iA}(z)\}_{i=1}^k \mid z \in g^{-1}(y)\} & \text{if } g^{-1}(y) \neq \phi \\ (0, 0, \dots, 0) & \text{k times, otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$$f_{g(A)}(y) = \begin{cases} \inf\{f_{iA}(z)\}_{i=1}^k \mid z \in g^{-1}(y)\} & \text{if } g^{-1}(y) \neq \phi \\ (1, 1, \dots, 1) & \text{k times, otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

for $y \in Y$, where $g^{-1}(y) = \{x \mid g(x) = y\}$

Let B be a Multi vague set in Y with dimension k . Then the inverse image of B i.e., $g^{-1}(B)$ is the Multi vague set of X with dimension k is given by

$$t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x) = t_{iB}(g(x)) \}_{i=1}^k \text{ and } f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x) = f_{iB}(g(x)) \}_{i=1}^k$$

Example 3.2 Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a homomorphism with $g(x) = x^2, \forall x \in X$ $X = \{1, -1, i, -i\}$ and $Y = \{1, -1\}$ be two groups.

A is a Multi vague set with dimension 4 in X .

B is a Multi vague set with dimension 4 in Y .

$$A = \{ \langle 1, (0.7, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2), (0.3, 0.5, 0.4, 0.3) \rangle, \\ \langle -1, (0.6, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1), (0.3, 0.6, 0.5, 0.4) \rangle, \\ \langle i, (0.5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2), (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.4) \rangle, \\ \langle -i, (0.5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2), (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.4) \rangle \}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 B &= \{ \langle 1, (0.7, 0.6, 0.5, 0.4), (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.4) \rangle, \\
 &\quad \langle -1, (0.6, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2), (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2) \rangle \} \\
 g(A) &= \{ \langle 1, (0.7, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2), (0.3, 0.5, 0.4, 0.3) \rangle, \\
 &\quad \langle -1, (0.5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2), (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.4) \rangle \}
 \end{aligned}$$

*B is a Multi vague set in Y then $g^{-1}(B)(x) = (t_{g^{-1}(B)}(x), f_{g^{-1}(B)}(x)), \forall x \in X$.
 where $t_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) = t_B(g(x))$ & $f_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) = f_B(g(x))$
 $t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x) = t_{iB}(g(x))\}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x) = f_{iB}(g(x))\}_{i=1}^k$*

$$\begin{aligned}
 B &= \{ \langle 1, (0.7, 0.6, 0.5, 0.4), (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.4) \rangle, \\
 &\quad \langle -1, (0.6, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2), (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2) \rangle \} \\
 g^{-1}(B) &= \{ \langle 1, (0.7, 0.6, 0.5, 0.4), (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.4) \rangle, \\
 &\quad \langle -1, (0.7, 0.6, 0.5, 0.4), (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.4) \rangle, \\
 \dots &\quad \langle i, (0.6, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2), (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2) \rangle, \\
 &\quad \langle -i, (0.6, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2), (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2) \rangle \}
 \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.3 *A Multi vague set A with dimension k in a set X is said to have sup property if for any subset $T \subset X, \exists t_0 \in T$ such that $A(t_0) = (t_A(t_0), f_A(t_0))$ where $t_A(t_0) = \sup\{t_{1A}(t_0), t_{1A}(t_0), \dots, t_{1A}(t_0), \forall t \in T\}$ $f_A(t_0) = \inf\{f_{1A}(t_0), f_{1A}(t_0), \dots, f_{1A}(t_0), \forall t \in T\}$ where $A = (t_A, f_A), t_A = (t_{1A}, t_{2A}, \dots, t_{kA})$ and $f_A = (f_{1A}, f_{2A}, \dots, f_{kA})$*

Theorem 3.4 *Let G and G' be groups and g be a homomorphism, from G into G'. Let b be a Multi vague group of a group of a group G' with dimension k. Then, the inverse image of $g^{-1}(B)$ is a Multi vague group in G. Further, if B is Multi vague normal group, then $g^{-1}(B)$ is also a Multi vague normal group.*

Proof: Let G and G' be groups.

$g : G \rightarrow G'$ is a homomorphism.

Let B is a Multi vague group of G' with dimension k.

Claim: $g^{-1}(B)$ is a Multi vague group of G.

(A Multi vague set $A = (t_A, f_A)$ of dimension k of a group G is said to be a Multi vague group of G if, for all $x, y \in G$,

- 1 $t_A(xy) \geq t_A(x) \wedge t_A(y)$ and $t_A(x^{-1}) = t_A(x)$
- 2 $f_A(xy) \leq f_A(x) \vee f_A(y)$ and $f_A(x^{-1}) = f_A(x)$

i.e.,

- 1 $t_{iA}(xy) \geq t_{iA}(x) \wedge t_{iA}(y)$ and $t_{iA}(x^{-1}) = t_{iA}(x)$
- 2 $f_{iA}(xy) \leq f_{iA}(x) \vee f_{iA}(y)$ and $f_{iA}(x^{-1}) = f_{iA}(x)$ for all $i=1,2,3,\dots,k$.

Equivalently, we define Multi vague group as, for all $x, y \in G$,
 $t_{iA}(xy^{-1}) \geq t_{iA}(x) \wedge t_{iA}(y)$, and $f_{iA}(xy^{-1}) \leq f_{iA}(x) \vee f_{iA}(y)$, and $i=1,2,\dots,k$.)

Consider $g^{-1}(B)(x) = (t_{g^{-1}(B)}(x), f_{g^{-1}(B)}(x)) = (t_B(g(x)), f_B(g(x)), \forall x \in X$.
 and $t_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) = t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x)\}_{i=1}^k$ and $f_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) = f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x)\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\therefore g^{-1}(B)(xy) = (t_{g^{-1}(B)}(xy), f_{g^{-1}(B)}(xy))$
 consider $t_{g^{-1}(B)}(xy) = t_B(g(xy)) = t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(xy)\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\geq t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x) \wedge t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k$ ($\because B$ is a Multi vague group)
 $= t_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) \wedge t_{g^{-1}(B)}(y)$
 $= t_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) \wedge t_{g^{-1}(B)}(y)$
 $\therefore t_{g^{-1}(B)}(xy) \geq t_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) \wedge t_{g^{-1}(B)}(y) \rightarrow (1)$

Also consider $f_{g^{-1}(B)}(xy) = f_B(g(xy)) = f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(xy)\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\leq f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x) \vee f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k$ ($\because B$ is a Multi vague group)
 $= f_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) \vee f_{g^{-1}(B)}(y)$
 $= f_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) \vee f_{g^{-1}(B)}(y)$
 $\therefore f_{g^{-1}(B)}(xy) \leq f_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) \vee f_{g^{-1}(B)}(y) \rightarrow (2)$

consider $t_{g^{-1}(B)}(x^{-1}) = t_B(g(x^{-1})) = t_{iB}(g(x^{-1}))\}_{i=1}^k$
 $= t_{iB}((g(x))^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k$ ($\because g$ is homomorphism)
 $= t_{iB}((g(x))^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k$ ($\because B$ is a Multi vague group).
 $= t_B(g(x)) = t_{g^{-1}(B)}(x)$
 $\therefore t_{g^{-1}(B)}(x^{-1}) = t_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) \rightarrow (3)$

consider $f_{g^{-1}(B)}(x^{-1}) = f_B(g(x^{-1})) = f_{iB}(g(x^{-1}))\}_{i=1}^k$
 $= f_{iB}((g(x))^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k$ ($\because g$ is homomorphism)
 $= f_{iB}((g(x))^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k$ ($\because B$ is a Multi vague group).
 $= f_B(g(x)) = f_{g^{-1}(B)}(x)$
 $\therefore f_{g^{-1}(B)}(x^{-1}) = f_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) \rightarrow (4)$

from (1), (2), (3) and (4)
 $t_{g^{-1}(B)}(xy) \geq t_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) \wedge t_{g^{-1}(B)}(y)$ & $t_{g^{-1}(B)}(x^{-1}) = t_{g^{-1}(B)}(x)$
 $f_{g^{-1}(B)}(xy) \leq f_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) \vee f_{g^{-1}(B)}(y)$ & $f_{g^{-1}(B)}(x^{-1}) = f_{g^{-1}(B)}(x)$
 $\therefore g^{-1}(B)$ is a Multi vague group of G .

Suppose B is Multi vague normal then,
 we have $t_{iB}(xy) = t_{iB}(yx)\}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{iB}(xy) = f_{iB}(yx)\}_{i=1}^k$
 claim: $g^{-1}(B)$ is vague normal group.

consider $t_{g^{-1}(B)}(xy) = t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(xy)\}_{i=1}^k = t_{i(B)}g(xy)\}_{i=1}^k$
 $= t_{i(B)}g(yx)\}_{i=1}^k (\because B \text{ is Multi vague normal}).$
 $= t_B(g(yx)) = t_{g^{-1}(B)}(yx)$
 $\therefore t_{g^{-1}(B)}(xy) = t_{g^{-1}(B)}(yx) \rightarrow (5)$
 Also consider $f_{g^{-1}(B)}(xy) = f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(xy)\}_{i=1}^k = f_{i(B)}g(xy)\}_{i=1}^k$
 $= f_{i(B)}g(yx)\}_{i=1}^k (\because B \text{ is Multi vague normal}).$
 $= f_B(g(yx)) = f_{g^{-1}(B)}(yx)$
 $\therefore f_{g^{-1}(B)}(xy) = f_{g^{-1}(B)}(yx) \rightarrow (6)$
 from (5) and (6) $f_{g^{-1}(B)}(xy) = f_{g^{-1}(B)}(yx) \ \& \ f_{g^{-1}(B)}(xy) = f_{g^{-1}(B)}(yx)$
 $\therefore g^{-1}(B) \text{ is a Multi vague normal group.}$

Theorem 3.5 Let A be a Multi vague group of a group G with dimension \mathbf{k} and G' be a group. Suppose $g : G \rightarrow G'$ is an epimorphism then $g(A)$ is a Multi vague group of G' .

Proof: Given A is a Multi vague group of a group G with dimension \mathbf{k} $A = (t_A, f_A)$, where $t_A(x) = (t_{1A}(x), t_{2A}(x), \dots, t_{kA}(x))$ and $f_A(x) = (f_{1A}(x), f_{2A}(x), \dots, f_{kA}(x))$ and $t_{1A}(x) \geq t_{2A}(x) \geq \dots \geq t_{kA}(x)$ where $0 \leq t_i + f_i \leq 1$, for $i=1, 2, \dots, k$.

Let $u, v \in G'$, then $u = g(x) \ \& \ v = g(y)$ for some $x, y \in G$

$$(\text{def } t_{g(A)}(x) = \begin{cases} \sup\{t_A(z) \mid z \in g^{-1}(x) \text{ if } g^{-1}(x) \neq \phi\} & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore t_{g(A)}(uv) &= t_{ig(A)}(uv)\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= \sup\{t_{iA}(xy) \mid xy \in g^{-1}(uv)\}_{i=1}^k \\ &\geq \sup\{t_{iA}(xy) \mid xy \in G, \exists g(x) = u, g(y) = v\}_{i=1}^k \\ &\geq \sup\{\min(t_{iA}(x), t_{iA}(y)) \mid xy \in G, \exists g(x) = u, g(y) = v\}_{i=1}^k \text{ (} A \text{ is a Multi vague group)} \\ &= \min\{\sup t_{iA}(x), \sup t_{iA}(y), x, y \in G \exists g(x) = u, g(y) = v\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= \min\{\sup t_{iA}(x) \mid g(x) = u, \sup t_{iA}(y) \mid g(y) = v\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= \min\{\sup t_{iA}(x) \mid x \in g^{-1}(u), \sup t_{iA}(y) \mid y \in g^{-1}(v)\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= \min\{t_{ig(A)}(u), t_{ig(A)}(v)\}_{i=1}^k = \min\{t_{g(A)}(u), t_{g(A)}(v)\} \\ \therefore t_{g(A)}(uv) &\geq \min\{t_{g(A)}(u), t_{g(A)}(v)\} \rightarrow (7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{also } (\text{def } f_{g(A)}(x) = \begin{cases} \inf\{f_A(z) \mid z \in g^{-1}(x) \text{ if } g^{-1}(x) \neq \phi\} & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore f_{g(A)}(uv) &= f_{ig(A)}(uv)\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= \inf\{f_{iA}(xy) \mid xy \in g^{-1}(uv)\}_{i=1}^k \\ &\leq \inf\{f_{iA}(xy) \mid xy \in G, \exists g(x) = u, g(y) = v\}_{i=1}^k \\ &\leq \inf\{\min(f_{iA}(x), f_{iA}(y)) \mid xy \in G, \exists g(x) = u, g(y) = v\}_{i=1}^k \text{ (} A \text{ is a Multi vague group)} \\ &= \max\{\inf f_{iA}(x), \inf f_{iA}(y), x, y \in G \exists g(x) = u, g(y) = v\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= \max\{\inf f_{iA}(x) \mid g(x) = u, \inf f_{iA}(y) \mid g(y) = v\}_{i=1}^k \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \max\{\inf f_{iA}(x) \mid x \in g^{-1}(u), \inf f_{iA}(y) \mid y \in g^{-1}(v)\}_{i=1}^k \\
 &\max\{f_{ig(A)}(u), f_{ig(A)}(v)\}_{i=1}^k = \max\{f_{g(A)}(u), f_{g(A)}(v)\} \\
 \therefore f_{g(A)}(uv) &\leq \max\{f_{g(A)}(u), f_{g(A)}(v)\} \rightarrow (8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{consider } t_{g(A)}u^{-1} = t_{ig(A)}(u^{-1})_{i=1}^k \\
 &= \sup\{t_{iA}(x^{-1}) \mid x^{-1} \in g^{-1}(u)\}_{i=1}^k \\
 &(\because \text{let } g(x) = u^{-1} \Rightarrow g(x)^{-1} = (u^{-1})^{-1} \\
 &\Rightarrow g(x^{-1}) = u \text{ (} g \text{ is homomorphism)} \Rightarrow x^{-1} \in g^{-1}(x)) \\
 &= \sup\{t_{i(g(A))}(u)\}_{i=1}^k = t_{g(A)}(u) \\
 \therefore t_{g(A)}(u^{-1}) &= t_{g(A)}(u), \forall u \in G'
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{consider } f_{g(A)}u^{-1} = f_{ig(A)}(u^{-1})_{i=1}^k \\
 &= \inf\{f_{iA}(x^{-1}) \mid x^{-1} \in g^{-1}(u)\}_{i=1}^k \\
 &(\because \text{let } g(x) = u^{-1} \Rightarrow g(x)^{-1} = (u^{-1})^{-1} \\
 &\Rightarrow g(x^{-1}) = u \text{ (} g \text{ is homomorphism)} \Rightarrow x^{-1} \in g^{-1}(x)) \\
 &= \inf\{f_{i(g(A))}(u)\}_{i=1}^k = f_{g(A)}(u) \\
 \therefore f_{g(A)}(u^{-1}) &= f_{g(A)}(u), \forall u \in G'
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \therefore t_{g(A)}(uv) &\geq \min\{t_{g(A)}(u), t_{g(A)}(v)\} \ \& \ t_{g(A)}(u^{-1}) = t_{g(A)}(u) \ \text{and} \\
 f_{g(A)}(uv) &\leq \max\{f_{g(A)}(u), f_{g(A)}(v)\} \ \& \ f_{g(A)}(u^{-1}) = f_{g(A)}(u), \forall u, v \in G' \\
 \Rightarrow g(A) &\text{ is a Multi vague subgroup of } G'
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.6 Let A be a Multi vague normal group of a group G with dimension k , and G' be a group. Suppose g is an epimorphism G onto G' . Then $g(A)$ is a Multi vague normal group of G' .

Proof: Given A is a Multi vague normal group of a group G with dimension k
 $A = (t_A, f_A)$, where $t_A(x) = (t_{1A}(x), t_{2A}(x), \dots, t_{kA}(x))$ and
 $f_A(x) = (f_{1A}(x), f_{2A}(x), \dots, f_{kA}(x))$ and $t_{1A}(x) \geq t_{2A}(x) \geq \dots \geq t_{kA}(x)$
 where $0 \leq t_i + f_i \leq 1$, for $i=1, 2, \dots, k$.
 and $g : G \rightarrow G'$ is an epimorphism.

Since A is Multi vague normal group of G .

$$\begin{aligned}
 t_A(xyx^{-1}) &= t_A(y) \ \& \ f_A(xyx^{-1}) = f_A(y) \\
 \text{i.e., } t_{iA}(xyx^{-1}) &= t_{iA}(y)_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{iA}(xyx^{-1}) = f_{iA}(y)_{i=1}^k
 \end{aligned}$$

claim: $g(A)$ is a Multi vague normal group of G'

Let $x, y \in G'$, since g is a surjection $g(a) = x, g(b) = y$ for some $a, b \in G$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{consider } t_{g(A)}(xyx^{-1}) = t_{ig(A)}(xyx^{-1})_{i=1}^k \\
 &= \sup\{t_{iA}(z) \mid z \in G, z \in g^{-1}(xyx^{-1})_{i=1}^k\} \ \& \ f_{g(A)}(xyx^{-1}) \neq \phi \\
 &(\text{let } g(z) = xyx^{-1}, \text{ then } g(z) = g(a)g(b)(g(a))^{-1} = g(a)g(b)g(a)^{-1} \text{ (} \because g \text{ is homo)}) \\
 \therefore g(z) &= g(aba^{-1}) \Rightarrow z = g^{-1}(g(aba^{-1}))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\Rightarrow a^{-1}za = a^{-1}(aba^{-1})a \\ &\Rightarrow a^{-1}za = (a^{-1}a)b(a^{-1}a) \\ &\Rightarrow a^{-1}za = b \\ &\Rightarrow a^{-1}za = g^{-1}(y) \\ &\Rightarrow g(a^{-1}za) = y \\ &\text{so replace } z \text{ with } a^{-1}za \text{ in the definition.} \\ &= \sup\{t_{iA}(a^{-1}za) \mid a^{-1}za \in G, g(a^{-1}za) = y\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= \sup\{t_{iA}(z) \mid aza^{-1} \in G, g(a^{-1}(aza^{-1})a) = y\}_{i=1}^k \text{ (} A \text{ is a Multi vague normal group.)} \\ &= \sup\{t_{iA}(z) \mid z \in G, g(z) = y\}_{i=1}^k \\ &t_{ig(A)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k = t_{g(A)}(y) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{consider } f_{g(A)}(xyx^{-1}) = f_{ig(A)}(xyx^{-1})_{i=1}^k \\ &= \inf\{f_{iA}(z) \mid z \in G, z \in g^{-1}(xyx^{-1})_{i=1}^k \text{ if } g^{-1}(xyx^{-1}) \neq \phi \\ &\text{(let } g(z) = xyx^{-1}, \text{ then } g(z) = g(a)g(b)(g(a))^{-1} = g(a)g(b)g(a)^{-1} \text{ (}\cdot\text{:}g \text{ is homo)} \\ &\therefore g(z) = g(aba^{-1}) \Rightarrow z = g^{-1}(g(aba^{-1})) \\ &\Rightarrow a^{-1}za = a^{-1}(aba^{-1})a \\ &\Rightarrow a^{-1}za = (a^{-1}a)b(a^{-1}a) \\ &\Rightarrow a^{-1}za = b \\ &\Rightarrow a^{-1}za = g^{-1}(y) \\ &\Rightarrow g(a^{-1}za) = y \\ &\text{so replace } z \text{ with } a^{-1}za \text{ in the definition.} \\ &= \inf\{f_{iA}(a^{-1}za) \mid a^{-1}za \in G, g(a^{-1}za) = y\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= \inf\{f_{iA}(z) \mid aza^{-1} \in G, g(a^{-1}(aza^{-1})a) = y\}_{i=1}^k \text{ (} A \text{ is a Multi vague normal group.)} \\ &= \inf\{f_{iA}(z) \mid z \in G, g(z) = y\}_{i=1}^k \\ &f_{ig(A)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k = f_{g(A)}(y) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\therefore t_{ig(A)}(xyx^{-1}) = t_{ig(A)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k \text{ \& } f_{ig(A)}(xyx^{-1}) = f_{ig(A)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k \\ &\text{i.e., } t_{g(A)}(xyx^{-1}) = t_{g(A)}(y) \text{ \& } f_{g(A)}(xyx^{-1}) = f_{g(A)}(y) \\ &\therefore g(A) \text{ is a Multi vague normal group.} \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.7 Let g be any mapping from a set X into a set Y and let A be, any Multi vague group of X with dimension \mathbf{k} , then A is called g - invariant, if $g(x) = g(y) \Rightarrow t_A(x) = t_A(y)$ & $f_A(x) = f_A(y), \forall x, y \in X$ (i.e., if $g(x) = g(y) \Rightarrow t_{iA}(x) = t_{iA}(y)\}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{iA}(x) = f_{iA}(y)\}_{i=1}^k, \forall x, y \in X$)

Remark 3.8 If A is a Multi vague group of Y with dimension \mathbf{k} , then $g^{-1}(A)$ is always g -invariant.

Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $g(x) = g(y)$.

$$t_{g^{-1}(A)}(x) = t_{ig^{-1}(A)}(x)\}_{i=1}^k = t_{i(A)}g(x)\}_{i=1}^k$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= t_{i(A)}g(y)\}_{i=1}^k = t_{ig^{-1}(A)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k = t_{g^{-1}(A)}(y) \\
 \therefore t_{g^{-1}(A)}(x) &= t_{g^{-1}(A)}(y) \\
 f_{g^{-1}(A)}(x) &= f_{ig^{-1}(A)}(x)\}_{i=1}^k = f_{i(A)}g(x)\}_{i=1}^k \\
 &= f_{i(A)}g(y)\}_{i=1}^k = f_{ig^{-1}(A)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k = f_{g^{-1}(A)}(y) \\
 \therefore f_{g^{-1}(A)}(x) &= f_{g^{-1}(A)}(y) \text{ for } g(x) = g(y) \\
 \Rightarrow t_{g^{-1}(A)}(x) &= t_{g^{-1}(A)}(y) \ \& \ f_{g^{-1}(A)}(x) = f_{g^{-1}(A)}(y) \\
 \Rightarrow g^{-1}(A) &\text{ is } g\text{-invariant.}
 \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.9 Let A be a Multi vague group of set X . We say that A is constant on a subset Y of X if $t_A(y_1) = t_A(y_2) \ \& \ f_A(y_1) = f_A(y_2) \ \forall y_1, y_2 \in Y$
i.e., $t_{iA}(y_1) = t_{iA}(y_2)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{iA}(y_1) = f_{iA}(y_2)\}_{i=1}^k \ \forall y_1, y_2 \in Y$

Theorem 3.10 Let $g : G \rightarrow G'$ be a homomorphism of groups. Let A, B be Multi vague groups of G and G' respectively then,

(i) $t_{g(A)}(e') = t_A(e) \ \& \ f_{g(A)}(e') = f_A(e)$
i.e., $t_{ig(A)}(e') = t_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{ig(A)}(e') = f_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k$ where e and e' are the identity elements in G and G' respectively.

(ii) $g(GV_A) \subseteq G'(v_g(A))$

i.e., $g(Gt_A) \subseteq G'(t_g(A))$ and $g(Gf_A) \supseteq G'(f_g(A))$

(iii) If A has sup property then $g(GV_A) = G'(v_g(A))$

i.e., $g(Gt_A) = G'(t_g(A))$ and $g(Gf_A) = G'(f_g(A))$

Proof: Given $g : G \rightarrow G'$ be a homomorphism of groups.

Let A, B be Multi vague groups of G and G' respectively with dimension k then $g(e) = e' \Rightarrow e \in g^{-1}(e')$

where e, e' being the identity elements of G and G' respectively.

(by the definition of

$$t_{g(A)}(x) = \begin{cases} \sup\{t_A(z) \mid z \in g^{-1}(x) \text{ if } g^{-1}(x) \neq \phi\} & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\text{i.e., } t_{ig(A)}(x)\}_{i=1}^k = \begin{cases} \sup\{t_{iA}(z) \mid z \in g^{-1}(x) \text{ if } g^{-1}(x) \neq \phi\}\}_{i=1}^k & \text{if } x = 0 \\ (0, 0, \dots, 0) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \text{ and}$$

$$f_{g(A)}(x) = \begin{cases} \inf\{f_A(z) \mid z \in g^{-1}(x) \text{ if } g^{-1}(x) \neq \phi\} & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\text{i.e., } f_{ig(A)}(x)\}_{i=1}^k = \begin{cases} \inf\{f_{iA}(z) \mid z \in g^{-1}(x) \text{ if } g^{-1}(x) \neq \phi\}\}_{i=1}^k & \text{if } x = 0 \\ (1, 1, \dots, 1) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{Now } t_{g(A)}(e') = t_{ig(A)}(e')\}_{i=1}^k \\
 &\sup\{t_{iA}(z) \mid z \in g^{-1}(e') \text{ if } g^{-1}(x) \neq \phi\}\}_{i=1}^k (\because e \in g^{-1}(e') \Rightarrow g^{-1}(e') \neq \phi) \\
 &(\text{ but } t_{iA}(e) \geq t_{iA}(z) \forall z \in G.) \\
 &= t_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k = t_A(e)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore t_{g(A)}(e') = t_A(e)$$

Now $f_{g(A)}(e') = f_{ig(A)}(e')\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\inf\{f_{iA}(z) \mid z \in g^{-1}(e') \text{ if } g^{-1}(x)\}\}_{i=1}^k (\because e \in g^{-1}(e') \Rightarrow g^{-1}(e') \neq \phi)$
 (but $f_{iA}(e) \leq t_{iA}(z) \forall z \in G.$)

$$= f_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k = f_A(e)$$

$$\therefore f_{g(A)}(e') = f_A(e)$$

$$\therefore t_{g(A)}(e') = t_A(e) \ \& \ f_{g(A)}(e') = f_A(e) \Rightarrow g(A)(e') = A(e)$$

$$(ii) \ GV_A = \{x \in G \mid t_A(x) = t_A(e) \ \& \ f_A(x) = f_A(e)\}$$

$$i.e., \ GV_A = \{x \in G \mid t_{iA}(x) = t_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{iA}(x) = f_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k \} \rightarrow (9)$$

$$G'V_A = \{x' \in G' \mid t_{g(A)}(x') = t_{g(A)}(e') \ \& \ f_{g(A)}(x') = f_{g(A)}(e')\}$$

$$i.e., \ G'V_A = \{x' \in G' \mid t_{ig(A)}(x') = t_{ig(A)}(e')\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{ig(A)}(x') = f_{ig(A)}(e')\}_{i=1}^k \}$$

Let $x' \in g(GV_A) \Rightarrow \exists x \in GV_A \ni g(x) = x'$

$$\therefore x \in GV_A \Rightarrow t_{iA}(x) = t_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k \text{ from (9)}$$

$$\text{consider } t_{g(A)}(x') = t_{ig(A)}(x')\}_{i=1}^k = \sup\{t_{iA}(p) \mid p \in g^{-1}(x')\}\}_{i=1}^k$$

$$= \sup t_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k = t_A(e)$$

$$\therefore t_{g(A)}(x') = t_A(e)$$

but $t_A(e) = t_{g(A)}(e')$ (from condition (i))

$$\therefore t_{g(A)}(x') = t_{g(A)}(e')$$

$$\text{similarly } f_{g(A)}(x') = f_{ig(A)}(x')\}_{i=1}^k = \inf\{f_{iA}(p) \mid p \in g^{-1}(x')\}\}_{i=1}^k$$

$$= \inf f_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k = f_A(e)$$

$$\therefore f_{g(A)}(x') = f_A(e)$$

but $f_A(e) = f_{g(A)}(e')$ (from condition (i))

$$\therefore f_{g(A)}(x') = f_{g(A)}(e')$$

Now for $x' \in g(VA_A)$, we have $t_{g(A)}(x') = t_{g(A)}(e') \ \& \ f_{g(A)}(x') = f_{g(A)}(e')$

$$\Rightarrow x' \in G'V_g(A)$$

$$\therefore g(GV_A) \subseteq G'V_g(A)$$

(iii) If A has supremum property then $g(GV_A) = G'V_g(A)$

feom condition (ii) $g(GV_A) \subseteq G'V_g(A)$

Claim: $G'V_g(A) \subseteq g(GV_A)$

Suppose A has supremum property (def A multi vague set A with dimension k with dimension k in a set X is said to have sup property, if for any subset $T \subset X, \exists t_0 \in T$ such that $A(t_0) = (t_A(t_0), t_A(t_0))$)

where $t_A(t_0) = \sup\{t_{1A}(p), t_{1A}(p), \dots, t_{1A}(p)\} \forall p \in T.$

and $f_A(t_0) = \inf\{f_{1A}(p), f_{1A}(p), \dots, f_{1A}(p)\} \forall p \in T.$)

Let $x' \in G'V_g(A).$

$\Rightarrow t_g(A)(x') = t_g(A)(e') = t_A(e)$ (from condition(i))
 $\therefore t_A(e) = t_{g(A)}(x') = t_{ig(A)}(x')\}_{i=1}^k$
 $= \sup\{t_{iA}(p) \mid p \in g^{-1}(x')\}$
 $= t_{iA}(a)\}_{i=1}^k (\exists a \in g^{-1}(x') \text{ by sup property})$
 $= t_A(a)$
 similarly $\Rightarrow f_g(A)(x') = f_g(A)(e') = f_A(e)$ (from condition(i))
 $\therefore f_A(e) = f_{g(A)}(x') = f_{ig(A)}(x')\}_{i=1}^k$
 $= \inf\{f_{iA}(p) \mid p \in g^{-1}(x')\}$
 $= f_{iA}(a)\}_{i=1}^k (\exists a \in g^{-1}(x') \text{ by sup property})$
 $= f_A(a) \therefore t_A(a) = t_A(e) \ \& \ f_A(a) = f_A(e) \Rightarrow a \in GV_A$
 for $a \in g^{-1}(x') \Rightarrow x' = g(a) \in g(GV_A)$
 $\therefore x' \in G'V_g(A) \Rightarrow x' \in g(GV_A)$
 $\Rightarrow G'V_g(A) \subseteq g(GV_A) \rightarrow (10)$
 from (9) & (10) $g(GV_A) = G'V_g(A)$
 Hence proved.

Theorem 3.11 let $g : G \rightarrow G'$ be a homomorphism of a group. Let A and B be Multi vague groups of G and G' with dimension k respectively, then (i) $g^{-1}(G'V_A) = GV_{g^{-1}(A)}$ (ii) if g is onto $g(g^{-1}(x')) = A$ i.e., $V_g(g^{-1}(x')) = V_A(x')$

Proof: Given $g : G \rightarrow G'$ be a homomorphism of a group.

A and B are Multi vague groups of G and G' with dimension k respectively.

For any $x \in G$, Let $x \in g^{-1}(G'V_A)$

$g(x) \in G'V_A$
 $\Leftrightarrow t_A(g(x)) = t_A(e') \ \& \ t_A(g(x)) = t_A(e')$
 $\Leftrightarrow t_{iA}(g(x)) = t_{iA}(e')\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ t_{iA}(g(x)) = t_{iA}(e')\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\Leftrightarrow t_{iA}(g(x)) = t_{iA}(g(e))\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ t_{iA}(g(x)) = t_{iA}(g(e))\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\Leftrightarrow t_{ig^{-1}(A)}(x) = t_{ig^{-1}(A)}(e)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ t_{ig^{-1}(A)}(x) = t_{ig^{-1}(A)}(e)\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\Leftrightarrow t_{g^{-1}(A)}(x) = t_{g^{-1}(A)}(e) \ \& \ t_{g^{-1}(A)}(x) = t_{g^{-1}(A)}(e)$
 $x \in GV_{g^{-1}(A)}$
 $\therefore g^{-1}(G'V_A) = GV_{g^{-1}(A)}$

(2) Let g be onto and $x' \in G'$

then, there exists $x \in G$, such that $x' = g(x)$

we have $t_{g(g^{-1}(A))}(x') = t_{g(g^{-1}(A))}g(x) = t_{ig(g^{-1}(A))}g(x)\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\sup\{t_{ig^{-1}(A)}(p) \mid p \in g^{-1}(g(x))\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\sup\{t_{iA}g(p) \mid p \in g^{-1}(g(x))\}_{i=1}^k$
 $= t_{iA}g(x)\}_{i=1}^k = t_{iA}(x')\}_{i=1}^k = t_{iA}(x')$
 $\therefore t_{g(g^{-1}(A))}(x') = t_{iA}(x'), \forall x' \in G'$
 $\Rightarrow t_{g(g^{-1}(A))} = t_A$

also consider $f_{g(g^{-1}(A))}(x') = f_{g(g^{-1}(A))}g(x) = f_{ig(g^{-1}(A))}g(x)\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\text{Inf}\{f_{ig^{-1}(A)}(p) \mid p \in g^{-1}(g(x))\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\text{Inf}\{f_{iA}g(p) \mid p \in g^{-1}(g(x))\}_{i=1}^k$
 $= f_{iA}g(x)\}_{i=1}^k = f_{iA}(x')\}_{i=1}^k = f_{iA}(x')$
 $\therefore f_{g(g^{-1}(A))}(x') = f_{iA}(x'), \forall x' \in G'$
 $\Rightarrow f_{g(g^{-1}(A))} = f_A$
 Hence $t_{g(g^{-1}(A))}(x') = t_A(x')$ & $f_{g(g^{-1}(A))}(x') = f_A(x')$
 $\therefore V_{g(g^{-1}(A))}(x') = V_A(x')$

Theorem 3.12 *Let g be a homomorphism from a group G into a group G' and let B be a Multi vague group with Sup property, then the pre-image $g^{-1}(B)$ is a Multi vague group of G with Sup property.*

Proof: Let $g : G \rightarrow G'$ be a homomorphism, where G and G' are groups.

B be a Multi vague group with dimension \mathbf{k} ,

then $B = (t_B, f_B)$ where $t_B(x) = (t_{1B}(x), t_{2B}(x), \dots, t_{kB}(x))$ and

$f_B(x) = (f_{1B}(x), f_{2B}(x), \dots, f_{kB}(x))$ and $t_{iB} : X \rightarrow [0, 1], f_{iB} : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, are mappings such that $t_{iB}(x) + f_{iB}(x) \leq 1$, for all $x \in X$, for $i=1,2,3,\dots,k$.

Here $t_{1B}(x) \geq t_{2B}(x) \geq \dots t_{kB}(x)$, for all $x \in X$.

$t_{iB}(xy^{-1}) \geq t_{iB}(x) \wedge t_{iB}(y)$, and $f_{iB}(xy^{-1}) \leq f_{iB}(x) \vee f_{iB}(y)$, and $i=1,2,\dots,k$.

Let $X \subseteq G$ be any subset then,

$t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x) = t_{iB}g(x)\}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x) = f_{iB}g(x)\}_{i=1}^k, \forall x \in X$

clearly g^{-1} is Multi vague group by the theorem (2.2.3)

consider $\text{sup}\{t_{g^{-1}B}(x) \mid x \in X\}$
 $= \text{sup}\{t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x) \mid x \in X\}_{i=1}^k$
 $= \text{sup}\{t_{iB}(g(x)) \mid x \in X\}_{i=1}^k$
 $= \text{sup}\{t_{iB}(y) \mid y \in g(X)\}_{i=1}^k \rightarrow (11)$
 $= \text{sup}\{t_B(y) \mid y \in g(X)\}$

B has sup property $\Rightarrow \exists y_0 \mid \text{ing}(X)$ such that

$t_B(y_0) = \text{sup}\{t_{iB}(y) \mid y \in g(X)\}_{i=1}^k \rightarrow (12)$

and $f_B(y_0) = \text{inf}\{f_{iB}(y) \mid y \in g(X)\}_{i=1}^k \rightarrow (13)$

from (1)&(2) $t_B(y_0) = \text{sup}\{t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x) \mid x \in X\}_{i=1}^k \rightarrow (14)$

also consider consider $\text{inf}\{f_{g^{-1}B}(x) \mid x \in X\}$

$= \text{inf}\{f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x) \mid x \in X\}_{i=1}^k$
 $= \text{inf}\{f_{iB}(g(x)) \mid x \in X\}_{i=1}^k$
 $= \text{inf}\{f_{ig^{-1}B}(y) \mid y \in g(X)\}_{i=1}^k \rightarrow (15)$
 $= \text{inf}\{f_B(y) \mid y \in g(X)\}$

from (12)&(15) $f_B(y_0) = \text{inf}\{f_{ig^{-1}B}(x) \mid x \in X\}_{i=1}^k$

$\therefore t_B(y_0) = \text{sup}\{t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x) \mid x \in X\}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_B(y_0) = \text{inf}\{f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x) \mid x \in X\}_{i=1}^k$ As

$y_0 \in g(X), \exists x_0 \in X$ such that $y_0 = g(x_0)$
 $\therefore t_{g^{-1}(B)}(x_0) = t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x_0)\}_{i=1}^k = t_{iB}(y_0)\}_{i=1}^k$
 $= \sup\{t_{ig^{-1}(y)}(x) \mid x \in X\}\}_{i=1}^k = \sup\{t_{g^{-1}(y)}(x) \mid x \in X\}$
 also $f_{g^{-1}(B)}(x_0) = f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x_0)\}_{i=1}^k = f_{iB}(y_0)\}_{i=1}^k$
 $= \inf\{f_{ig^{-1}(y)}(x) \mid x \in X\}\}_{i=1}^k = \inf\{f_{g^{-1}(y)}(x) \mid x \in X\}$
 so, $\exists x_0 \in X, \exists t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x_0)\}_{i=1}^k = \sup\{t_{ig^{-1}(y)}(x) \mid x \in X\}\}_{i=1}^k$ and
 $f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x_0)\}_{i=1}^k = \inf\{f_{ig^{-1}(y)}(x) \mid x \in X\}\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\therefore g^{-1}(B)$ has supremum property.

Theorem 3.13 Let g be epimorphism from G onto group G' and let A, B be Multi vague groups with dimension k , of G and g' respectively then,

- (1) if $MVO_A(x) = n (< \infty)$, then $VO_{g(A)}(g(x)) = VO_A(x), \forall x \in G$
- (2) $MVO_{g(B)}(g(x)) = MVO_{g^{-1}(B)}(x), \forall x \in G$.

Proof: Let $MVO_A(x) = n$,

follows that $t_{iA}(x^n) = t_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{iA}(x^n) = f_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k \rightarrow (16)$

since $g : G \rightarrow G'$ is an epimorphism, there exists a 'x' in G such that $g(x) = y \Rightarrow g^{-1}(y)$ is non empty.

consider $t_{g(A)}[g(x)]^n = t_{ig(A)}[g(x)]^n\}_{i=1}^k = t_{ig(A)}[g(x)^n]\}_{i=1}^k$ ($\because g$ is homomorphism)
 $= \sup\{t_{iA}(z) \mid z \in g^{-1}(g(x^n))\}\}_{i=1}^k$
 (let $z = x^n$) $= \sup\{t_{iA}(x^n) \mid x^n \in g^{-1}(Y)\}\}_{i=1}^k$
 $= t_{iA}(x^n)\}_{i=1}^k = t_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k$ from (16)
 $\geq t_{ig(A)}[(g(x))^n]\}_{i=1}^k$ ($\because t_{iA}(e) \geq t_{iA}(x), \forall x \in G$)
 $= t_{g(A)}[(g(x))^n]$
 $\therefore t_{ig(A)}[g(x)]^n\}_{i=1}^k = t_{iA}(x^n)\}_{i=1}^k$

also consider $f_{g(A)}[g(x)]^n = f_{ig(A)}[g(x)]^n\}_{i=1}^k = f_{ig(A)}[g(x)^n]\}_{i=1}^k$ ($\because g$ is homo)
 $= \inf\{f_{iA}(z) \mid z \in g^{-1}(g(x^n))\}\}_{i=1}^k$
 (let $z = x^n$) $= \inf\{f_{iA}(x^n) \mid x^n \in g^{-1}(Y)\}\}_{i=1}^k$
 $= f_{iA}(x^n)\}_{i=1}^k = f_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k$ from (16)
 $\leq f_{ig(A)}[(g(x))^n]\}_{i=1}^k$ ($\because f_{iA}(e) \leq f_{iA}(x), \forall x \in G$)
 $= f_{g(A)}[(g(x))^n]$
 $\therefore f_{ig(A)}[g(x)]^n\}_{i=1}^k = f_{iA}(x^n)\}_{i=1}^k$

$$\therefore t_{ig(A)}[g(x)]^n\}_{i=1}^k = t_{iA}(x^n)\}_{i=1}^k \text{ \& } f_{ig(A)}[g(x)]^n\}_{i=1}^k = f_{iA}(x^n)\}_{i=1}^k \rightarrow (17)$$

Also we have $t_{ig(A)}(g(x)) = t_{iA}(x)\}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{ig(A)}(g(x)) = f_{iA}(x)\}_{i=1}^k$

$$\Rightarrow t_{ig(A)}(g(e)) = t_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k \text{ \& } f_{ig(A)}(g(e)) = f_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k \rightarrow (18)$$

Let $MVO_{g(x)} = l$ and $MVO_A(x) = n$

since $MVO_A(x) = n$

$$\Rightarrow t_{ig(A)}(x^n) = t_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k \text{ \& } f_{ig(A)}(x^n) = f_{iA}(e)\}_{i=1}^k \rightarrow (19)$$

from (17), (18)&(19)

$$t_{ig(A)}[g(x)]^n = t_{ig(A)}g(e)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{ig(A)}[g(x)]^n = f_{ig(A)}g(e)\}_{i=1}^k$$

$$\Rightarrow t_{g(A)}[g(x)]^n = t_{g(A)}g(e) \ \& \ f_{g(A)}[g(x)]^n = f_{g(A)}g(e)$$

but $MVO_{g(A)} = l \Rightarrow l|n$
i.e., $MVO_{g(A)}(g(x)) | MVO_A(x) \rightarrow (20)$

Here $MVO_g(A)(g(x)) = l$
 $\Rightarrow t_{ig(A)}[g(x)]^l = t_{ig(A)}g(e)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{ig(A)}[g(x)]^l = f_{ig(A)}g(e)\}_{i=1}^k$
 but $MVO_A(x) = n \Rightarrow n|l \rightarrow (21)$
i.e., $MVO_A(x) | MVO_{g(A)}(g(x))$
 from (20)&(21) $\Rightarrow MVO_{g(A)}(g(x)) = MVO_A(x)$

Claim: $MVO_B(g(x)) = MVO_{g^{-1}(B)}(x), \forall x \in G$
 Let $MVO_B(g(x)) = n \ \& \ MVO_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) = m$
 $MVO_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) = m \Rightarrow t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x^m) = t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(e)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x^m) = f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(e)\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\Rightarrow t_{i(B)}(g(x^m)) = t_{i(B)}g(e)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{i(B)}(g(x^m)) = f_{i(B)}(g(e))\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\Rightarrow t_{i(B)}(g(x))^m = t_{i(B)}g(e)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{i(B)}(g(x))^m = f_{i(B)}(g(e))\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\therefore MVO_B(g(x)) = n$
 $\Rightarrow n|m \rightarrow (22)$

Now consider $MVO_B(g(x)) = m$
 $\Rightarrow t_{i(B)}(g(x))^m = t_{i(B)}(e')\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{i(B)}(g(x))^m = f_{i(B)}(e')\}_{i=1}^k$
 (where e' is the identity in G')
 $\Rightarrow t_{i(B)}(g(x)^m) = t_{i(B)}(e')\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{i(B)}(g(x)^m) = f_{i(B)}(e')\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\Rightarrow t_{i(B)}(g(x)^m) = t_{i(B)}g(e)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{i(B)}(g(x)^m) = f_{i(B)}(g(e))\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\Rightarrow t_{ig^{-1}(B)}((x)^m) = t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(e)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{ig^{-1}(B)}((x)^m) = f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(e)\}_{i=1}^k$
 but $MVO_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) = m$
 $\therefore m|n \rightarrow (23)$
 from (22)&(23) $\Rightarrow m = n$
 $\therefore MVO_B(g(x)) = MVO_{g^{-1}(B)}(x), \forall x \in G$

Theorem 3.14 Let g be a group epimorphism from group G onto G' respectively with dimension \mathbf{k} .

- (1) If A has condition (II) and A is g - invariant, then $g(A)$ has condition (II)
- (2) If B has condition (II), then $g^{-1}(B)$ has condition (II)

Proof: Given $g : G \rightarrow G'$ is an epimorphism

A is a Multi vague group of G with dimension G with dimension \mathbf{k} . B is a Multi vague group of G' with dimension G with dimension \mathbf{k} . (1) Given Multi vague A has condition (II) [*i.e.*, $MVO_A(x) = MVO_A(y) \Rightarrow t_{iA}(x) = t_{iA}(y)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{iA}(x) = f_{iA}(y)\}_{i=1}^k$

claim: $t_{g(A)}(g(x)) = t_{g(A)}(g(y))\}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{g(A)}(g(x)) = f_{g(A)}(g(y))\}_{i=1}^k$
 claim: $t_{g(A)}(g(x)) = t_{g(A)}(g(y))$ & $f_{g(A)}(g(x)) = f_{g(A)}(g(y))$
 i.e., $t_{ig(A)}(g(x)) = t_{ig(A)}(g(y))\}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{ig(A)}(g(x)) = f_{ig(A)}(g(y))\}_{i=1}^k$
 Suppose $MVO_{g(A)}g(x) = MVO_{g(A)}g(y)$
 by the above theorem $[MVO_{g(A)} = MVO_A(x)]$
 $\Rightarrow MVO_A(x) = MVO_A(y)$ (condition II, since A obey)
 $\Rightarrow t_{iA}(x) = t_{iA}(y)\}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{iA}(x) = f_{iA}(y)\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\Rightarrow t_{ig(A)}(x) = t_{ig(A)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{ig(A)}(x) = f_{ig(A)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\Rightarrow t_{g(A)}(x) = t_{g(A)}(y)$ & $f_{g(A)}(x) = f_{g(A)}(y)$
 \therefore for $MVO_{g(A)}g(x) = MVO_{g(A)}(g(y))$
 $\Rightarrow t_{ig(A)}(g(x)) = t_{ig(A)}(g(y))\}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{ig(A)}(g(x)) = f_{ig(A)}(g(y))\}_{i=1}^k$
 $g(A)$ also obey condition II

(2) Let Multi vague group B has condition (II) for every integer n,
 $[i.e., MVO_B(g(x)) = MVO_B(g(y))]$
 $\Rightarrow t_{iB}(g(x)) = t_{iB}(g(y))\}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{iB}(g(x)) = f_{iB}(g(y))\}_{i=1}^k$
 claim: If $[MVO_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) = MVO_{g^{-1}(B)}(y)]$
 $\Rightarrow t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x) = t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k$ & $f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(x) = f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k$ Let $MVO_{g^{-1}(B)}(x) = MVO_{g^{-1}(B)}(y)$
 $\Rightarrow MVO_B(g(x)) = MVO_B(g(y))$ (by the definition)
 $\Rightarrow t_{iB}(g(x)) = t_{iB}(g(y))\}_{i=1}^k$ & $t_{iB}(g(x)) = t_{iB}(g(y))\}_{i=1}^k$ (\therefore B satisfies condition II)
 $\Rightarrow t_{ig^{-1}B}(x) = t_{ig^{-1}B}(y)\}_{i=1}^k$ & $t_{ig^{-1}B}(x) = t_{ig^{-1}B}(y)\}_{i=1}^k$
 $\therefore g^{-1}(B)$ satisfies condition (II)

Theorem 3.15 Let g be a group epimorphism from G to group G'. Let A, B be vague groups of G and G' respectively with dimension k, then

$t_{g(A)}(y) \leq t_B(y)$ & $t_{g(A)}(y) \geq t_B(y)$ iff $t_B(g(x)) \geq t_A(x)$ & $f_B(g(x)) \leq f_A(x), \forall x \in G, y \in G'$

i.e., $t_{ig(A)}(y) \leq t_{iB}(y)\}_{i=1}^k$ & $t_{ig(A)}(y) \geq t_{iB}(y)\}_{i=1}^k$ iff $t_B(ig(x)) \geq t_{iA}(x)\}_{i=1}^k$
 & $f_{iB}(g(x)) \leq f_{iA}(x)\}_{i=1}^k, \forall x \in G, y \in G'$

Proof: Case I: Suppose $t_{g(A)}(y) \leq t_B(y)$ & $f_{g(A)}(y) \geq f_B(y), \forall y \in G'$

Here $t_{g(A)}(y) = \sup\{t_A(x) | x \in G, x \in g^{-1}(y)\}$ ($\because g^{-1}(y) \neq \phi$)

and $f_{g(A)}(y) = \inf\{f_A(x) | x \in G, x \in g^{-1}(y)\}$

Let $x \in G, \&g(x) = y$

then $t_{iA}(x) \leq t_{ig(A)}(x) \leq t_{iB}(y) \leq t_{iB}(g(x))\}_{i=1}^k$

$\Rightarrow t_A(x) \leq t_{g(A)}(x) \leq t_B(y) \leq t_B(g(x))$

$\Rightarrow t_A(x) \leq t_B(g(x))$

$t_B(g(x)) \geq t_A(x) \rightarrow (24)$

similarly $f_{iA}(x) \geq f_{ig(A)}(x) \geq f_{iB}(y) \geq f_{iB}(g(x))\}_{i=1}^k$

$\Rightarrow f_A(x) \geq f_{g(A)}(x) \geq f_B(y) \geq f_B(g(x))$

$\Rightarrow f_A(x) \geq f_B(g(x))$
 $f_B(g(x)) \leq f_A(x) \rightarrow (25)$
 from (24)&(25) we have $t_B(g(x)) \geq t_A(x) \ \& \ f_B(g(x)) \leq f_A(x)$

Case II: conversely, suppose $t_B(g(x)) \geq t_A(x) \ \& \ f_B(g(x)) \leq f_A(x)$
 i.e., $t_{iB}(g(x)) \geq t_{iA}(x) \}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{iB}(g(x)) \leq f_{iA}(x) \}_{i=1}^k$
 Let $y \in G'$, let $x \in g^{-1}(y) \Rightarrow g(x) = y$
 $\Rightarrow t_{iB}(y) = t_{iB}(g(x)) \geq t_{iA}(x) \}_{i=1}^k$
 $\Rightarrow t_B(y) = t_B(g(x)) \geq t_A(x)$
 $\because t_B(g(x))$ is an upper bound of $\{t_A(x) | x \in G, x \in g^{-1}(y)\}$
 but $t_{g(A)}(y) = \sup\{t_A(x) | x \in g^{-1}(y)\}$
 $\therefore t_{g(A)}(y) \leq t_B(g(x))$
 $\Rightarrow t_{g(A)}(y) \leq t_B(y) \rightarrow (26)$

similarly $\Rightarrow f_{iB}(y) = f_{iB}(g(x)) \leq f_{iA}(x) \}_{i=1}^k$
 $\Rightarrow f_B(y) = f_B(g(x)) \leq f_A(x)$
 $\because f_B(g(x))$ is an upper bound of $\{f_A(x) | x \in G, x \in g^{-1}(y)\}$
 but $f_{g(A)}(y) = \inf\{f_A(x) | x \in g^{-1}(y)\}$
 $\therefore f_{g(A)}(y) \geq f_B(g(x))$
 $\Rightarrow f_{g(A)}(y) \geq f_B(y) \rightarrow (27)$
 from (26)&(27) we have $t_{g(A)}(y) \leq t_B(y) \ \& \ f_{g(A)}(y) \geq f_B(y)$

Theorem 3.16 Let $g : G \rightarrow G'$ be a homomorphism of groups. Let A be a Multi vague group of G with dimension \mathbf{k} , then A is g -invariant iff A is constant on $\ker g$.

Proof: Given $g : G \rightarrow G'$ be a homomorphism of group

A is a Multi vague group of G with dimension \mathbf{k}

Case I: Suppose A is constant on $\ker g$.

claim: A is g -invariant.

If $x \in \ker g \Rightarrow t_{iA}(x) = t_{iA}(e) \}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{iA}(x) = f_{iA}(e) \}_{i=1}^k$

Let $g(x) = g(y) \Rightarrow g(xy^{-1}) = g(e)$

$\Rightarrow xy^{-1} \in \ker g$

$\therefore t_{iA}(xy^{-1}) = t_{iA}(e) \}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{iA}(xy^{-1}) = f_{iA}(e) \}_{i=1}^k$

$t_{iA}(x) = t_{iA}(y) \}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{iA}(x) = f_{iA}(y) \}_{i=1}^k$

$\Rightarrow A$ is g invariant.

Conversely suppose A is g -invariant for for any $x \in \ker g$, we have $g(x) = g(e)$

$\Rightarrow t_{iA}(x) = t_{iA}(e) \}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{iA}(x) = f_{iA}(e) \}_{i=1}^k$

$\therefore A$ is constant on $\ker g$.

Hence theorem proved.

Theorem 3.17 *Let g be a homomorphism of an abelian group G onto an abelian group G' . Let A and B be Multi vague groups of G with dimension \mathbf{k} , such that $A \subseteq B$, then $g(N(A)) \subseteq N(g(A))$.*

Proof: Given $g : G \rightarrow G'$ is an onto homomorphism.

G and G' are abelian groups.

A and B are Multi vague groups of G with dimension \mathbf{k} , such that $A \subseteq B$

$$N(A) = \{a \in G \mid t_{iA}(axa^{-1}) = t_{iA}(x)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{iA}(axa^{-1}) = f_{iA}(x)\}_{i=1}^k, \forall x \in G\}$$

Let $x \in g(N(A))$, then $\exists u \in N(A), \because g(u) = x$ for all $y \in G'$

$$\text{then } g(N(A)) = \{g(a) \in G' \mid a \in G, t_{iA}(axa^{-1}) = t_{iA}(x)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{iA}(axa^{-1}) = f_{iA}(x)\}_{i=1}^k, \forall x \in G\}$$

$$\text{and } N(g(A)) = \{x \in G' \mid t_{ig(A)}(xyx^{-1}) = t_{ig(A)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{ig(A)}(xyx^{-1}) = f_{ig(A)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k, \forall y \in G'\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{consider } t_{g(A)}(xyx^{-1}) &= t_{ig(A)}(xyx^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k = t_{i(A)}(g^{-1}(xyx^{-1}))\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= t_{i(A)}(g^{-1}(x)g^{-1}(y)g^{-1}(x^{-1}))\}_{i=1}^k = t_{i(A)}(g^{-1}(x)g^{-1}(y)(g^{-1}(x))^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k (\because g \text{ is homo}) \\ &= t_{i(A)}(g^{-1}(g(u))g^{-1}(g(v))(g^{-1}(g(u)))^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k \text{ where } g(v) = y, \forall v \in G \\ &= t_{iA}g^{-1}(g(uv u^{-1}))\}_{i=1}^k = t_{iA}(v)\}_{i=1}^k = t_{iA}(g^{-1}(y))\}_{i=1}^k = t_{ig(A)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= t_g(A)(y) \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore t_{ig(A)}(xyx^{-1}) = t_{ig(A)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k, \text{ for all } y \in G'$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{similarly } f_{g(A)}(xyx^{-1}) &= f_{ig(A)}(xyx^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k = f_{i(A)}(g^{-1}(xyx^{-1}))\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= f_{i(A)}(g^{-1}(x)g^{-1}(y)g^{-1}(x^{-1}))\}_{i=1}^k = f_{i(A)}(g^{-1}(x)g^{-1}(y)(g^{-1}(x))^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k (\because g \text{ is homo}) \\ &= f_{i(A)}(g^{-1}(g(u))g^{-1}(g(v))(g^{-1}(g(u)))^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k \text{ where } g(v) = y, \forall v \in G \\ &= f_{iA}g^{-1}(g(uv u^{-1}))\}_{i=1}^k = f_{iA}(v)\}_{i=1}^k = f_{iA}(g^{-1}(y))\}_{i=1}^k = f_{ig(A)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= f_g(A)(y) \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore f_{ig(A)}(xyx^{-1}) = f_{ig(A)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k, \text{ for all } y \in G'$$

$$\therefore t_{ig(A)}(xyx^{-1}) = t_{ig(A)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{ig(A)}(xyx^{-1}) = f_{ig(A)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k, \text{ for all } y \in G' \\ \Rightarrow x \in N(g(A))$$

Hence $g(N(A)) \subseteq N(g(A))$.

Theorem 3.18 *Let $g : G \rightarrow G'$ be a homomorphism of abelian groups G and G' . Let A and B be Multi vague groups of $G' \ni B \subseteq A$, then $g^{-1}(N(B)) = N(g^{-1}(B))$*

Proof: Let $x \in g^{-1}(N(B))$, then for all $y \in G$

$$\begin{aligned} g^{-1}(N(B)) &= \{a \in G \mid g(a) \in N(B)\} \\ &= \{a \in G \ \& \ t_{iB}(g(a)yg(a)^{-1}) = t_{iB}(y)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{iB}(g(a)yg(a)^{-1}) = f_{iB}(y)\}_{i=1}^k, \forall y \in G\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{and } N(g^{-1}(B)) = \{x \in G \mid t_{ig^{-1}B}(xyx^{-1}) = t_{ig^{-1}(B)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{ig^{-1}B}(xyx^{-1}) = f_{ig^{-1}(B)}(y)\}_{i=1}^k, \forall y \in G\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} t_{g^{-1}B}(xyx^{-1}) &= t_{ig^{-1}B}(xyx^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k = t_{iB}(g(xy x^{-1}))\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= t_{iB}(g(x)g(y)g(x^{-1}))\}_{i=1}^k = t_{iB}(g(x)g(y)(g(x))^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k (\because G' \text{ is abelian}) \\ &= t_{iB}(g(y))\}_{i=1}^k = t_{ig^{-1}B}(y)\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= t_{g^{-1}(B)}(y) \\ \therefore t_{ig^{-1}B}(xyx^{-1}) &= t_{ig^{-1}B}(y)\}_{i=1}^k \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{similarly } f_{g^{-1}B}(xyx^{-1}) &= f_{ig^{-1}B}(xyx^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k = f_{iB}(g(xy x^{-1}))\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= f_{iB}(g(x)g(y)g(x^{-1}))\}_{i=1}^k = f_{iB}(g(x)g(y)(g(x))^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k (\because G' \text{ is abelian}) \\ &= f_{iB}(g(y))\}_{i=1}^k = f_{ig^{-1}B}(y)\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= f_{g^{-1}(B)}(y) \\ \therefore f_{ig^{-1}B}(xyx^{-1}) &= f_{ig^{-1}B}(y)\}_{i=1}^k \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore t_{ig^{-1}B}(xyx^{-1}) &= t_{ig^{-1}B}(y)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{ig^{-1}B}(xyx^{-1}) = f_{ig^{-1}B}(y)\}_{i=1}^k \\ \Rightarrow x \in N(g^{-1}(B)) \\ \text{So, } g^{-1}(N(B)) &\subseteq N(g^{-1}(B)) \rightarrow (28) \end{aligned}$$

Again, let $x \in N(g^{-1}(B))$
 and $g(x) = u$, then for all $v \in G'$

$$\begin{aligned} t_B(uvu^{-1}) &= t_{iB}(uvu^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= t_{iB}(g(x)g(y)(g(x))^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k \text{ where } (y \in G \ni g(y) = v) \\ &= t_{iB}(g(y)g(x)(g(x))^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k (\because G' \text{ is abelian}) \\ &= t_{iB}(g(y))\}_{i=1}^k = t_{iB}(v)\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= t_B(v) \\ \therefore t_{iB}(uvu^{-1}) &= t_{iB}(v)\}_{i=1}^k \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{similarly } f_B(uvu^{-1}) &= f_{iB}(uvu^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= f_{iB}(g(x)g(y)(g(x))^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k \text{ where } (y \in G \ni g(y) = v) \\ &= f_{iB}(g(y)g(x)(g(x))^{-1})\}_{i=1}^k (\because G' \text{ is abelian}) \\ &= f_{iB}(g(y))\}_{i=1}^k = f_{iB}(v)\}_{i=1}^k \\ &= f_B(v) \\ \therefore f_{iB}(uvu^{-1}) &= f_{iB}(v)\}_{i=1}^k \\ \therefore t_{iB}(uvu^{-1}) &= t_{iB}(v)\}_{i=1}^k \ \& \ f_{iB}(uvu^{-1}) = f_{iB}(v)\}_{i=1}^k \\ \Rightarrow u \in N(B), \text{ i.e., } x &\in g^{-1}(N(B)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{So, } N(g^{-1}(B)) &\subseteq g^{-1}(N(B)) \rightarrow (29) \\ \text{from (28) \& (29)} &\Rightarrow g^{-1}(N(B)) = N(g^{-1}(B)) \end{aligned}$$

It completes the proof.

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